

Figure 2A Uncropped Gel

Canine cardiac slices maintained in culture.

Gel images are chemiluminescence signal captured using a ChemiDoc XRS molecular imager (BioRad).

Figure 2E Uncropped Gel

Canine cardiac slices treated with autophagy modulators.

Gel images are chemiluminescence signal captured using a ChemiDoc XRS molecular imager (BioRad).

Figure 3D Uncropped Gel

Canine cardiac slices treated for 24 hours with various concentrations of doxorubicin.

Gel images are chemiluminescence signal captured using a ChemiDoc XRS molecular imager (BioRad).

Figure 4A Uncropped Gel

Canine cardiac slices treated with doxorubicin with or without rapamycin.

Gel images are chemiluminescence signal captured using a ChemiDoc XRS molecular imager (BioRad).

Figure S3 Uncropped Gel

Canine cardiac slices treated for 48 hours with various concentrations of doxorubicin.

Gel images are chemiluminescence signal captured using a ChemiDoc XRS molecular imager (BioRad).